

FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF 3D CARBON-CARBON COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The fracture toughnesses of three 3D C/C composites with different processing were evaluated using critical stress intensity factor K_{Ic} and work-of-fracture parameter R_f . The relations between fracture toughness and microstructure was studied on the basis of investigating fracture behaviors of 3D C/C composites.

INTRODUCTION

Very little data have been reported to date on the fracture toughness of 3D C/C composites. In this paper, the fracture toughness of three 3D C/C composites with different processing was determined using critical stress intensity factor K_{Ic} and work-of-fracture parameter R_f concepts. Moreover, the relations between fracture toughness and microstructure were studied on the basis of investigating fracture behaviors of 3D C/C composites, in order to get an improvement on fracture toughness in future processing of this kind of materials.

MATERIALS DESCRIPTIONS AND EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

1. MATERIALS

The characteristics of three 3D C/C composites in this study are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Characteristics of three 3D C/C composites

Material No.	1#	2#	3#
Woven constitution (X-Y-Z)	2-2-3 ₄	2-2-3	2-2-3
Pressure in processing	low	middle	high
Matrix	CVD-carbon +resin- carbon	pitch-carbon +resin- carbon	CVD-carbon +pitch-carbon
Bulk density(g/cm ³)	1.80	1.97	1.99
Open porosity (%)	5.14	3.85	4.03

2. Experimental Techniques

The specimens dimensions are shown in Fig.1. Z and X specimens mentioned in the following refer to the specimens with different sampling directions on 3D C/C composites. All the specimens were tested in three-point bending using a WD-30 modle testing machine under a deflection rate of 0.5 mm/min. The load-deflection curves were recorded using a X-Y recorder.

The critical stress intensity factor K_{Ic} and the work-of-fracture parameter R_f were given below 1:

$$K_c = \frac{P_{max} \cdot S}{B \cdot W^{3/2}} (2.9(a/w)^{1/2} - 4.6(a/w)^{3/2} + 21.8(a/w)^{5/2} - 37.6(a/w)^{7/2} + 38.7(a/w)^{9/2}) \quad (1)$$

$$R_f = \frac{U}{2B(W-a)} \quad (2)$$

where P_{max} is the maximum load on specimen (at inception of instability) and U is the total area under load-deflection curve.

In order to know fracture behaviors of 3D C/C composites, microstructure changes before and after P_{max} were examined by a MM-6 model metallagraph. Fracture surfaces of typical specimens were examined by a S 250 MK2 model SEM.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. K_c and R_f of the 3D C/C composites

The K_c and R_f values of Z and X specimens with notches of $a=1\text{mm}$ and $c=0.2\text{mm}$ for all 3D C/C composites are reported in Table 2. The values for KS-9 graphite are also contained in for comparison.

Table 2 The K_c and R_f values of 3D C/C composites and KS-9 graphite

Materials No. Sampling direction	1#		2#		3#		KS-9 (graphite)	
	Z	X	Z	X	Z	X	//	⊥
K_c (Mpa \sqrt{m})	5.98	5.64	8.11	5.08	6.60	4.50	0.70	0.68
R_f (KJ/m ²)	12.34	5.90	3.37	1.40	2.41	1.01	0.11	0.12

Table 2 shows that K_c values of three 3D C/C composites have not much difference, but are much higher than that of graphite. This indicates that 3D C/C composites have a higher resistance to crack initiation than graphite. For R_f , the values of 3D C/C composites are much different. It presents that the ability to resist both crack initiation and propagation is strongly dependent on processings. Obviously, R_f values of all 3D C/C composites are much higher than that of graphite. So 3D C/C composites have a great improvement on fracture toughness compared with graphite. Besides, both K_c and R_f of Z specimens are higher than that of X specimens for each composite. It mainly results from higher fiber content in Z direction.

The typical load-deflection curves for 1# and 2# Z specimens with three different notch depth a are shown in Fig.2 and the results calculated using equation (1) and (2) are reported in Table 3. Fig.3 illustrates the typical load-deflection curves for 1# X specimens with three different notch width c and results are reported in Table 4.

Table 3 The K_c and R_f values of 1# and 2# Z specimens with different notch depth

Specimen	a/W	K_c (Mpa m)	R_f (KJ/m)
1# Z	0.15	5.98	12.34
	0.29	6.08	5.30
	0.50	6.12	4.28
2# Z	0.15	8.11	3.37
	0.29	9.05	3.50
	0.50	7.84	2.23

$c=0.2\text{mm}$

Table 4 The K_c and R_f values of 1# X specimens with different notch width

Specimen	c(mm)	K_c (MPa m)	R_f (KJ/m)
1# X	0.20	5.64	5.90
	0.50	5.35	5.79
	1.00	5.66	6.25

$a/W=0.15$

Fig.2 shows that P_{max} and U decrease with the increase of notch depth a (or a/W). Table 3 indicates that R_f is not a material constant, but has a decreasing trend with the increase of a/W ratio, especially for 1#Z specimens. It seems that R_f is independent of notch width c , Table 4. By comparison, K_{Ic} is essentially independent of a/W ratio and c . This indicates that K_{Ic} can be considered as a material constant.

2. Fracture behaviors of 3D C/C composites

Fig.4 shows typical load-deflection curves of Z and X specimens of 3D C/C composites. Different curve shapes are found, which reflects different fracture behaviors. For 2# and 3# composites (esp. for 3#), they show some brittle fracture behaviors. But for 1# composites, the load-deflection responses are much different and it shows some plastic fracture behaviors. The curve to P_{max} is nonlinear and the load after P_{max} does not show a steep fall, but a relatively steady decrease with increase of deflection. Besides, it can be carefully seen from Fig.4 that for all 3D C/C composites, their curves after P_{max} appear in step-type shape. This is resulted from the discontinuous fracture behaviors which is presented below.

Fig.5 illustrates microstructure changes just before and after P_{max} . It could be seen that crack initiation was generally produced in the corner of notch bottom or on fiber-matrix interface, and extended along weak combined interface to transverse (direction along specimen length) fiber bundles. Because the load on specimen was not big enough to have the fiber bundle damaged, cracks on transverse fiber bundles had not been found before P_{max} , Fig.5 a. This indicates that, for all 3D C/C composites, the crack initiation on interface or even in matrix can not cause total damage of their specimens. But once the fiber bundle near notch was damaged, the specimen then could not support any higher load, Fig.5 b. After the first fiber bundle was damaged, the crack could not propagate across another fiber bundle quickly due to numerous microcracks pre-existed around fiber bundles. The stress at the tip of crack had to have a re-distribution. This will result in a small step on load-deflection curve. Other steps on curve could be get in this way. So the discontinuous fractures of fiber bundles then resulted in the step-type shape on load-deflection curves.

3. Relations Between Microstructure and K_{Ic} , R_f of 3D C/C composites

It is known that K_{Ic} and R_f values of each 3D C/C composite are different. Microstructure analysis revealed that 1# composites has a weak interface bonding. Its fiber bundles were pulled out when specimen was damaged, Fig.6a. But 3# composite has a relatively stronger interface bonding. Its fiber bundles were damaged like being cut off and a relatively smoother fracture surface was obtained. Fig.6b. The 2# composite interface bonding examined is between 1# and 3# composites.

The experimental data and microstructure analysis reveal that 3D C/C composites in which there are numerous microcracks around fibers and interface bonding is weak should have a higher R_f values, for a great quantity of energy will be needed to have fibers pulled-out and interface unbonded in whole fracture processes of both crack initiation and propagation. But those in which there are less microcracks and interface bonding is strong should have a low R_f value.

Because cracks initiation on interface or in matrix was produced before P_{max} , K_{Ic} is not a factor to present the ability to resist this type of crack initiation but of crack initiation across transverse fiber bundles. So microstructure of matrix within fiber bundles may have influence on K_{Ic} values. The matrix within 2# composite fiber bundles is a kind of POG (parallel oriented graphite). When initial crack propagates to the fiber bundles, the POG structure can prevent the crack crossing the bundles directly. This will result in a zigzag course of crack

initiation across fiber bundles, Fig.5b(2#) and Fig.7a. It will decrease stress concentration at the tip of crack and increase load on specimen before unstable crack growth occurs. So the POG structure within fiber bundles is of advantage to increase of K_c value. By comparison, the matrix within 3# composite fiber bundles is mainly a kind of TOG (transverse oriented graphite). It will make crack propagate easily across fiber bundles for the stress at tip of crack is concentrated very easily on fibers. This will result in a smaller P_{max} and smoother fracture surface, Fig.5b(3#), 6b and 7b. So the TOG structure within fiber bundles is of no advantage to increase of K_c value.

CONCLUSIONS

Concerning how to evaluate fracture toughness of 3D C/C composites, it is valuable using K_c to present the resistance to crack initiation across fiber bundles and R_f to present the resistance to both crack initiation and propagation, if microstructure analysis is also considered.

Within experimental scatter ($a/W=0.15-0.50$, $c=0.2-1.0mm$), K_c is essentially independent of a/W and c , and R_f is dependent of a/W . K_c can be considered a material constant but R_f not.

Discontinuous fracture behaviors of 3D C/C composite specimens were observed, which correspond to the step-type shape on load-deflection curves. It resulted from the fracture discontinuity of fiber bundles.

POG structure within 3D C/C composite fiber bundles is of advantage to increase of K_c value while TOG not. It can be explained by the influence of these structures on the course of crack initiation. 3D C/C composites which have numerous microcracks pre-existed around fibers and weak interface bonding will have a higher R_f value. But those which have dense structure and relatively strong interface bonding generally have a lower R_f value

REFERENCE

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S =span, 50mm L =length, 60mm
 B =width, 7mm, W =depth, 7mm
 a =notch length, c =notch width

Fig.1 Geometry of single-edge-notched fracture toughness bend specimen

Fig.2 Typical load-deflection curves of 1# and 2# Z specimens with different notch depth

Fig.3 Typical load-deflection curves of 1# X specimens with different notch width

Fig.4 Typical load-deflection curves of Z and X specimens for three 3D C/C composites

Fig.5 Microstructure changes before and after Pmax for each 3D C/C composite Z specimens (metallographs, 35 X)

Fig.6 Fracture surfaces of 1# and 3# X specimens (SEM)

Fig.7 The influence of two type of pitch-carbon structure within fiber bundles on the course of crack initiation